

MICROMECHANICS BASED FAILURE ANALYSIS OF LAMINATES UNDER OFF- AXIS LOADING

C. Marotzke*, R. Basan

BAM - Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing,
Division 5.6, Mechanical Behaviour of Polymers, Berlin, Germany

*Corresponding author (christian.marotzke@bam.de)

Keywords: *Composite Materials, Interface Crack, Failure Analysis, Adhesion*

Abstract

The debonding of a fiber in a glass fiber / epoxy composite under transverse loading is studied. The stress field in the interface as well as the energy release rate are analysed for two fiber volume fractions.

The circumferential propagation of an interface crack starting at the center of a fiber which is located within a hexagonal fiber array is studied. The analysis is performed by a finite element simulation under plane stress conditions. Two fiber volume fractions are considered, this is 30% and 70%. The stress distribution before and during crack propagation is calculated for different stages of the crack. The crack opens by dominating tensile stresses in the first phase while it closes when propagating along the interface. The total energy release rate as well as the mode I and mode II parts are calculated. In the first phase the crack is driven by an increasing mode I energy release rate, indicating an unstable crack propagation. Then the mode II energy release rate increases rapidly and dominates the debonding process while the mode I part decreases and finally vanishes. Subsequently also the mode II part decreases, indicating stable crack propagation. In the last phase the crack becomes unstable again due to a strongly increasing mode I energy release rate. During the debonding process a remarkable change the mode ratio takes place.

The main features of the debonding process are similar for low and high fiber volume fraction. In case of the high fiber content, however, the mode I part is more pronounced and the maximum of the total energy release rate is shifted to lower crack angles.

1 Introduction

Even though the strength of laminates is governed by the strength of the layers oriented predominantly in loading direction, the failure usually is initiated in the plies with the maximum transverse stresses. Although the plies transverse to the main loading direction are secondary in carrying the external load, the failure of those plies generally reduces the load carrying capability of the laminate. The analysis of failure under off-axis stresses accordingly is essential for the prediction of the strength of laminates. This is allowed for in failure criteria including inter fiber failure, proposed e.g. by Puck [1] and Cuntze [2]. Most of the inter fiber failure criteria are not based on the micromechanics of the failure process but on stress interaction functions. That is, these failure criteria, even though they are "mechanism based" on the macroscale, they are also phenomenological on the microscale. The failure of plies under transverse loading is a complex process, its fundamental phenomenon is the debonding of a single fiber. This was addressed theoretically, among others, by Paris et al. [3] and Correa et al. [4]. Experimental work was done by Tandon et al. [5] and Ogihara et al. [6] who studied the failure of single fibers under off-axis loading. A recent study was done by the author [7].

The failure of the fiber/matrix interface under off-axis loading is not easy to predict. In the vicinity of the interface the matrix has properties different from that of the bulk material, e.g. as a result of transcrystallinity. Accordingly, the matrix in the vicinity of the interface may have higher strength than away from the interface. Even the strength of the interface may higher than that of the bulk material. These problems were discussed in field of the measurement of the adhesion between fiber and matrix with micromechanical tests such as single

fiber pull-out and microdroplet tests [8,9,10]. Since these properties depend on the particular materials, especially on the surface treatment of the fibers, no general statement can be made whether the interface or the matrix in some distance from the interface will fail. The present study is based on the assumption that the failure of a ply under off-axis loading is initiated by interfacial failure and hence by the strength of the interface between fiber and matrix.

The stress field in the interface, which is governing the debonding process and, in turn, the energy release rate, strongly depends on the distance between the fibers, this is, on the fiber volume fraction. Two representative fiber volume fractions are investigated, a low one of 30% and a high one of 70%. The material used for this study is a glass fiber/epoxy composite. In two phase materials, the interface fails under mixed mode stresses. The mode ratio changes when the crack propagates in circumferential direction. In the present study the stresses in the interface are calculated for a crack starting in the center of the interface caused by the highest radial stresses and propagating symmetrically along the interface.

In the first part of the paper the stresses in the interface before crack initiation as well as during crack propagation are calculated. In the second part the mode I and mode II energy release rates are calculated for the respective volume fractions.

2 FEM Model

The analysis given here is limited to pure transverse loading, this is, to uniaxial normal stresses perpendicular to the fiber direction. A composite material with a hexagonal fiber arrangement is chosen. The debonding of the central fiber analysed. The respective fiber is surrounded by a full hexagonal cell which, in turn, is surrounded by one half of all next neighbours (fig. 1). On the edges of the model, symmetry conditions are prescribed. The load is applied via a prescribed displacements in x-direction on the right side of the model while the left side is fixed. During crack propagation the prescribed displacement remains unchanged, the crack propagation accordingly is analysed under "fixed grips" conditions.

The elements used are 8-node quadrilateral elements under plane stress conditions. In order to get comparable results for different fiber volume fractions the mesh in the vicinity of the interface is chosen identical for either fiber volume fraction. Two rows of almost quadratic elements are arranged on either side of the interface (4 rows in total), each corresponding to a 1° crack increment. In the interface, the adjacent fiber and matrix elements possess individual nodes which are glued together unless they are separated when the crack is forming. This allows the separate calculation of the stresses in the interface in either material.

Since at a specific crack length the crack closes again and the crack faces come into contact, contact elements are provided in the interface. Friction, however, is not taken into account in this study. The influence of friction will be addressed in a further study since the contact pressure is not negligible and will cause noteworthy frictional shear stresses.

Fig. 1: Finite element mesh of hexagonal composite - 30% and 70% fiber volume fraction

The loading is normalised in order to give the same maximum normal stresses, this is, in the interface at the center of the fiber. The idea behind this normalization is that the initiation of debonding is governed by these stresses. With this kind of loading, debonding starts at the same magnitude of maximum radial stresses in the interface, independent of fiber volume fraction. In case of high fiber volume fractions the stresses concentration near the center is higher than for low fiber volume fractions. As a result, the average stress in x-direction is lower for high volume fraction which, at first glance, may look inconsistent.

3 Stress Field in the Interface

3.1 Interfacial Stresses before Debonding

Analysing stresses in interfaces between dissimilar materials one should take into consideration that the stresses in the interface are different in the two phases when they are related to cutting planes not coinciding with planes tangential to the interface. That means that stresses given in the global coordinate system are different on either side of the interface, because they are related to cutting planes oriented in longitudinal direction (x-direction) or transverse direction (y-direction). Therefore, only the stresses normal and tangential to the interface are identical in fiber and matrix. The normal stresses are also referred to as radial stresses, the tangential stresses as shear stresses. They are denoted by S_n and S_t .

3.1.1 Interfacial Stresses

- Composite with Fiber Volume Fraction 30%

The stresses in the interface are shown in fig. 2a for a fiber volume fraction of 30%. Besides the radial and tangential stresses the stresses in x-direction in fiber and matrix are given. In the center, this is at 0° and 180° , the stresses in x-direction in fiber and matrix as well as the normal stress are identical because the cutting planes coincide with planes tangential to the interface. Moving in circumferential direction along the interface the stresses in the fiber decrease very little. According to their high stiffness the main load transfer takes place through the fibers. The stresses in the matrix on the other hand almost vanish at 90° . At this point they are parallel to the interface. In that region the deformation of the matrix in x-direction is constrained by the fiber, resulting in low matrix stresses. Since the neighbouring fibers in 60° and 120° direction are far away from the interface they have no significant influence on the interfacial stress distribution.

The radial stresses are, as expected, maximal in the center and decrease by a factor of ten at 90° , where they are oriented in y-direction. Comparing the stresses in the interface one should keep in mind that the direction of the radial stresses differs more and more from the x-direction proceeding in circumferential direction. Accordingly, although the matrix stresses and the radial stresses exhibit some

similarities there is no direct correlation between these two stresses except that they follow the general rule of the transformation of the stress vector. The tangential stresses (shear stresses) are maximal at 40° and vanish at 90° as this is a symmetry plane. The maximal shear stress is almost half of the maximal radial stress, this is, the shear stress will have significant influence on the debonding process.

Fig. 2a interfacial stresses - stresses in x-direction and normal/tangential to the interface $V_f = 30\%$

The large difference between the stresses in the center and on the top and bottom of the fiber (90°) is caused by the high differences of the stiffnesses which give rise to a very inhomogeneous distribution of the deformation field in the composite. The main deformation of the composite takes place in the matrix due to its seriously lower stiffness. According to the geometry of the fibers the strain distribution in the matrix is highly inhomogeneous. The distance between the surfaces of neighbouring fiber is minimal in the center and grows moving up- and downwards. As a result the strain in x-direction in the matrix increases when moving to the center, where the maximum is reached. This, in turn, leads to the strong increase of the matrix stresses towards the center.

3.1.1 Interfacial Stresses

- Composite with Fiber Volume Fraction 70%

If the fiber volume fraction is high, the characteristics of the load transfer through fiber and matrix change significantly. The concentration of the strains at the center becomes more pronounced for high fiber volume fractions. Following the considerations concerning the geometrical

conditions, the configuration changes as follows with higher fiber volume fraction. As a matter of course the distance between the fibers decreases for high fiber volume fractions. For the strains and in turn also for the stresses in x-direction, the relative change of the distance of neighbouring fiber surfaces is relevant. If the distance at the center (0°) is taken as a basis, the relative change of the distance is the total change of the distance divided by the distance at the center. Since the geometry of the fibers is invariant, the relative increase of the distance between neighbouring fiber surfaces is higher for high fiber volume fractions since it is related to a smaller basis (fig. 1). As a result, the strains in x-direction in the matrix decrease faster compared to the low fiber volume fraction. This applies also to the stresses in x-direction.

Fig. 2b interfacial stresses - stresses in x-direction and normal/tangential to the interface $V_f = 70\%$

The changes in the stress field become evident for the stresses in x-direction in the interface on the fiber side. While they are almost constant in case of low fiber volume fraction (fig. 2a) here they show a remarkable descent moving in circumferential direction. In contrast to the low fiber volume fraction the neighbouring fibers under 60° and 120° have a significant influence on the stresses in the interface. They are responsible for the second maximum at 90° . The influence on the stresses on the matrix side is less pronounced. The high stiffness of the neighbouring fibers causes the change of the slope in the respective region.

3.2 Interfacial Stresses during Debonding

In the mathematical description of a crack problems within the frame of elasticity theory, the stress field becomes singular at the tip of a crack. This is true also for cracks between dissimilar media even though the order of the singularity is not 0.5 anymore as known from homogeneous materials but depends on the elastic constants of the respective materials. Anyway, the stresses at the crack tip calculated by finite elements have in general no significance and are depending on the finite element mesh. However, the distributions of the stresses after some distance of the crack tip are reasonable.

Following the assumption made the debonding starts at the maximum of the tensile stresses, this is, at the center of the interface (0°). The crack is presumed to propagate symmetrically in both directions along the interface. The radial stresses are plotted for five phases of the crack in fig. 3a. The formation of the crack leads to a significant growth of the radial stresses in the zone ahead of the crack tip (crack angle $\alpha=30^\circ$). With further propagation of the crack the stresses near the crack tip decrease ($\alpha=60^\circ$). At a crack angle of $\alpha=90^\circ$, a contact zone has formed before the crack tip, ranging from 78° to the crack tip, giving rise to compressive stresses. For larger crack lengths the contact zone enlarges and the beginning slightly shifts along the interface. Due to the debonding, as a matter of fact, the load transfer through the fiber is strongly diminished. At the center of the bonded edge, this is, on the opposite side (180°), the decrease of the radial stresses becomes visible.

Fig. 3a: radial stresses in fiber-matrix interface during propagation of interface crack $V_f = 30\%$

The question arises how the fiber volume fraction influences the stresses in the interface during the debonding process. In fig. 3b the radial stresses for the low fiber volume fraction (30%) are compared with the those of the high volume fraction (70%) at two different crack lengths. At a crack angle of $\alpha=60^\circ$ the radial stresses in front of the crack tip are lower for the high fiber volume fraction but decrease somewhat slower. At 100° the slope becomes much steeper and the stresses change even to compressive. This again is a consequence of the vicinity of the neighbouring fibers. The radial stresses on the bonded edge show that the unloading of the fiber is higher for a high volume fraction. The compressive zone, which forms at larger crack angles, is smaller in case of the higher volume fraction.

Fig. 3b: radial stresses in fiber-matrix interface during propagation of interface crack - comparison of fiber volume fractions 30% and 70% at two stages of the crack

The unloading of the fiber is more pronounced in case of a high fiber volume fraction. This is due to the fact the neighbouring fibers attract more load due to their high stiffness. For a low fiber volume fraction there is no region of such high stiffness around the debonding fiber. The higher unloading of the debonding fiber in turn leads to an enlargement of the stresses in the adjacent fibers and increases the likelihood of debonding of the respective fibers.

4 Energy Release Rate during Debonding

4.1 Energy Release Rate for Fiber Volume Fraction 30%

The crack starts with a rapid growth of the mode I energy release rate (fig. 4b). Due to the radial tensile

stresses the crack opens (fig. 3a) in that phase. The maximum of the mode I energy release rate is reached at a crack angle of about 20° . Beyond the maximum the mode I part decreases and vanishes at about 50° . In contrast, the mode II part develops somewhat delayed but shows a very steep ascent beyond crack angle of about 10° . The maximum of the mode II energy release rate is reached at 60° . The maximum is much higher than that of the mode I part. During further crack propagation the crack closes, indicated by the compressive radial stresses in the interface (fig. 3a). As a result, the mode I part disappears. The mode II part decreases as well and vanishes at about 150° . Accordingly the total energy release rate also vanishes in that region. This means that the crack never would propagate beyond this zone and no total debonding of the fiber would arise, even though the external load would be heavily increased. Accordingly, the anew increase of the mode I energy release in the final stage is just theory.

Fig. 4a: Energy release rate during interfacial crack propagation for fiber volume fraction 30%

The debonding process is highly dominated by the mode II energy release rate. Even though the initiation of the interface crack is forced by radial tensile stresses the main phase of the debonding is driven by shear stresses. Just at the end the mode I part becomes relevant again.

4.2 Energy Release Rate for Fiber Volume Fraction 70%

In case of a fiber volume fraction of 70% the mode I energy release rate increases much faster reaching a higher maximum. At the same time the mode II part

grows slower and the maximum is significantly lower than for the low fiber volume fraction. Beyond an angle of 130° the course of the energy release rates are very similar for both fiber contents. Even though the mode I rate has more influence on the debonding process in both cases it is still the less important part, except of the initial phase of the crack.

Fig. 4b: Energy release rate during interfacial crack propagation for fiber volume fraction 70%

4.3 Stable versus unstable Crack Propagation

In both cases the total energy release rate shows a rapid growth in the beginning reaching a maximum within the first 45° of the crack. In classical linear elastic fracture mechanics the first phase of the crack is considered as unstable because the energy release rate increases, beyond the maximum it is considered as stable since the energy release rate decreases. This is a severe simplification of the actual fracture process, even if perfect elasticity is presumed. Only a part of the energy released by the crack is consumed by the generation of the crack surfaces. The excessive energy is transformed into kinetic energy in form of a shock wave. This shock wave will initiate further fiber debonds which obviously then develop under dynamic conditions, that means, different from the process studied here. The wave is reflected on the interfaces and a portion of the kinetic energy hits the first interface again. This will cause a further propagation of the crack. Accordingly it is not likely that the crack will stop instantaneously when the maximum of the energy release rate is reached but will still grow to some extent.

In a composite with a polymeric matrix there is an additional consumption of energy due to viscous effects as well as due to plasticity of the matrix. Hence, the linear elastic analysis of an interface crack can only give a limited insight into the actual behaviour of the inter fiber failure process. Experiments on single fibers under transverse loading interestingly show an unstable crack propagation up to 60° - 65° , which corresponds to the maximum of the energy release rate found in a composite with a fiber volume fraction of 5% [7]. This shows that in principle a stable phase during the interfacial crack propagation exists, even though the mechanisms are much more complex than covered by a linear elastic analysis.

References

- [1] A. Puck, H. Schürmann, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 58, pp 343-377, 1998.
- [2] R. G. Cuntze, A. Freund, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 64, pp 1045-1067, 2004.
- [3] F. Paris, E. Correa, J. Canas, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 63, pp 1041-1052, 2003.
- [4] E. Correa, E. K. Gamstedt, F. Paris, V. Mantic, *Composites Part A*, Vol. 38, pp 2260-2269, 2007.
- [5] G. P. Tandon, R. Y. Kim, V. T. Bechel, *Int. J. for Multiscale Computational Engineering*, Vol. 2, pp 65-77, 2004.
- [6] S. Ogihara, J. Koyanagi, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 70, pp 143, 2010.
- [7] C. Marotzke, *Proc. 14th Europ. Conf. on Composite Materials (ECCM 14)*, Budapest, 2010.
- [8] J. K. Kim, Y. W. Mai, *Engineered Interfaces in Fiber Reinforced Composites*, Elsevier, 1998.
- [9] E. Pisanova, S. Zhandarov, E. Mäder, I. Ahmad, R. J. Young, *Composites Part A*, Vol. 32, pp 435-443, 2001.
- [10] C. Marotzke, L. Qiao, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 57, pp 887-897, 1997.